

Statistical evaluation of fatigue test results of butt-weld connections with imperfections

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ABSTRACT

Welded connections are integral components of steel structures, commonly used in engineering applications such as bridges, cranes, and marine structures, all of which are subject to fatigue. The vulnerability of welded connections to fatigue, which can ultimately lead to failure, necessitates rigorous evaluation. Several documents, including prEN 1993-1-9, IIW recommendations, AWS codes, and EN 13001, have been developed to quantify the fatigue resistance of welded connections. Most of these references admit that the fatigue resistance depends on the quality of the welds with respect to external and/or internal imperfections. For instance, prEN 1993-1-9 requires the use of ISO 5817 quality level B for weld imperfections, despite a lack of comprehensive studies supporting this requirement. For this reason, an analysis of the extensive database established for prEN 1993-1-9 and of results published in different research papers, encompassing 3446 experimental fatigue tests results, has been performed. The present paper focuses exclusively on the test results of butt-weld connections. The primary objective is twofold: firstly, to conduct a qualitative assessment of the impact of various weld imperfections and execution parameters on the fatigue resistance, and secondly, to re-evaluate the necessity of quality level B as specified in prEN 1993-1-9. The fatigue resistance was determined following the statistical evaluation of fatigue test results, in accordance with the reliability criteria outlined in Eurocode 0. The study examines the effects of imperfections, such as inclusions, misalignment, incomplete root penetration, and porosities.

Keywords: Fatigue resistance, weld imperfections, butt-weld connections.

1 INTRODUCTION

Despite the precision and expertise that welders bring to their craft, welds are not immune to imperfections. These imperfections can potentially affect the structural integrity, reliability, and safety of a welded connection. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the causes contributing to the emergence of each weld imperfection. *Table 1* outlines possible causes of imperfections commonly encountered in practice during welding and sheds the light on how to mitigate and prevent them.

Most European standards used in several engineering applications recognize the link between weld imperfections and fatigue resistance. Examples are prEN 1993-1-9 (1) and EN 1090-2 (2) for steel construction, EN 13001 (3) for cranes, and EN 15085 (4) for railway vehicles. A similar approach is also provided in the requirements of the International Institute of Welding (IIW) (5).

All of these references link fatigue resistance to quality requirement according to ISO 5817 (6), which defines acceptance criteria for typical weld imperfections and classifies them into three quality levels: B, C, and D, with quality level B being the highest one. It should be noted that ISO 5817 is based on the former German standard DIN 8563 (7). The latter was developed to provide a common framework for interpreting results obtained from non-destructive testing (NDT) methods, such as ultrasonic

testing, radiographic testing, dye penetrant testing or magnetic particle testing. However, DIN 8563 was not initially intended to define quality levels that would be in relation to fatigue resistance. Although welding imperfections such as those shown in *Table 1* may affect fatigue resistance, the requirements outlined in various standards are based on limited studies and differ from one reference to another.

Table 1 : Common welding imperfections in butt-weld connections

Reference to ISO 6520-1 (8)	Imperfection designation	Representation	Causes (9, 10)
5011 5012	Undercut		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High welding amperage, – Incorrect electrode angle, – High welding speed.
4021	Lack of penetration		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Low welding amperage, – High welding speed, – Poor joints preparation.
5071	Linear misalignment		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Inadequate control during the setup.
2011	Porosities		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Moistures on base metal, – Atmospheric conditions (windy weather), – Damaged electrode flux.
300, 301, 302, 303	Inclusions		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Slag inclusions due to bad cleaning in multi-passes welding, – Inclusions caused by the welding process, such as silica inclusions from MAG, and tungsten inclusions from TIG.

In the field of steel construction, prEN 1993-1-9 (1) requires ISO 5817 (6) quality level B for all constructional details subject to fatigue. However, it may be questionable whether a particular ISO quality level is suitable for all constructional details, as not all imperfections have the same impact on the fatigue resistance, as will be shown throughout this paper. One may note that the requirement of ISO 5817 quality level B has been chosen in order to account for the uncertainty concerning the real quality of the welds that have been tested in the past for the development of prEN 1993-1-9 fatigue resistances (detail categories). Most of these tests were conducted between the 1950s and 1980s, a period during which no standardized specifications were provided for the performance of non-destructive tests to characterize imperfections. Moreover, welding technologies and inspection techniques employed in that era have evolved over time, resulting in increased weld quality and potentially increased weld resistance. Some of the tests documented in the EN 1993-1-9 background document (11, 12) were confirmed to contain weld imperfections. However, this information has not been exploited in detail up to now.

To minimize uncertainties, fatigue test results were grouped based on the studied parameter (imperfection type). Nonetheless, even within a same group, test results showed some scatter in the resistance due to other factors as plate thickness, welding process, and steel strength. Based on comparisons between these groups, this paper aims to provide a qualitative estimation of the effect of different types of imperfections and other parameters on the fatigue resistance.

2 DATA BASE EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

For the present study, 3446 fatigue tests have been analysed and presented on scatter graphs. These tests date from 1950s to 2023, and were carried out in different countries including, France, Germany, Japan, Spain, United Kingdom, and United States. In the framework of this paper, the assessment is

limited to butt-weld connections welded from one side and two sides. Future investigations are expected to be conducted for load-carrying cruciform joints.

In order to identify the effect of studied parameters on the fatigue resistance, the existing test database was subdivided into two main groups. A first group referred to as “full database” englobes all the fatigue tests mentioned in this paper. The specimens within the “full database” group comprise various welding processes (manual arc welding, automatic welding, submerged arc welding, flux-cored arc welding, metal active gas welding, tungsten inert gas welding, and laser welding) and different pre/post-welding conditions (preheated, as-welded, stress relieved, machined). Testing involved both tensile and bending loading, covering a range of positive and negative stress ratios. Some specimens in the “full database” were reported to contain imperfections (e.g. inclusions, misalignment) through non-destructive testing. Therefore, an assessment of their impact on fatigue resistance could be performed. A second subset referred to as “filtered database”, is identified. The parameters of the “filtered database” are as follows:

- Stress ratio: $R \geq 0$,
- Plate thickness: $t \leq 25$ mm,
- Yield strength: $f_y < 500$ MPa,
- As-welded condition,
- Tensile fatigue tests,
- No reported imperfections,
- All welding processes.

These parameters were selected based on their recognized influence on fatigue resistance in previous studies, an influence that will be further emphasized in this current investigation. It is important to clarify that “no reported imperfections” indicate that in certain instances, non-destructive testing was conducted, affirming the absence of imperfections in the welds, while in other cases, no deliberate effort was made to detect imperfections in the specimens.

When assessing the fatigue resistance of welded connections, it is necessary to refer to specific fatigue resistance curves, also known as S-N curves or Wöhler curves. These curves, established for example in prEN 1993-1-9 (1) for predefined detail categories, are associated to a unique shape characterized by the characteristic fatigue resistance “ $\Delta\sigma_c$ ” at two million cycles and a predefined slope “ m ”. The statistical evaluation method is used to determine these curves, establishing a lower prediction bound with 95% probability of survival and thus respecting the requirement of prEN 1990 (13). For the studied details, the slope proposed in prEN 1993-1-9 is $m=3$. Although it would be possible to determine a more suitable value of the slope, the authors chose to maintain the fixed slope of $m=3$, as the aim of this study is not to propose new fatigue resistance curves but to highlight the influence of different imperfections on the fatigue resistance of welded connections.

While analysing the database, authors were able to identify the impact of different parameters on the fatigue resistance of welded connections through comparisons of test groups based on a single variable parameter. Such impacts were also noticed in previous investigation. For example, the effect of stress ratio in a single-V butt-weld joints was revealed in studies (14-16) and that of weld geometry, particularly the flank angle, was recognised as a critical parameter affecting fatigue resistance in studies (17, 18), where machined specimens displayed higher fatigue strength in comparison to as-welded specimens. Additionally, parameters such as plate thickness, steel strength, and imperfections also have revealed an impact on fatigue resistance.

3 TRANSVERSE BUTT-WELD JOINT WELDED FROM ONE SIDE

According to prEN 1993-1-9 (1), the detail category (DC) DC 71 applies to full penetration transverse butt-weld joints welded from one side and verified by appropriate non-destructive tests (NDT). On the other hand, DC 36 applies to all other conditions. For this type of joint, prEN 1993-1-9 considers acceptable a maximum misalignment of 5% of plate thickness for both categories.

A comprehensive examination of 1052 tests from the “full database” was conducted for these joints. Out of these, 194 tests met the criteria set for the “filtered database”. *Table 2* provides detailed information and references for these selected 194 tests.

Table 2: Filtered database references and information for butt-weld joints welded from one side

Year	Reference	Number of specimens	f_y [MPa]	Plate thickness [mm]	Welding process
1959	Newman et al. (19)	26	277	12.7	Manual arc welding
1961	Nacher (16)	6	235	6	Manual arc welding
1962	Gurney (20)	36	298; 388	12.7	Manual arc welding
1966	Yamaguchi et al. (17)	31	265; 295; 345	10	Automatic welding
1970	Robakowski (21)	16	296	12	Manual arc welding
1975	Kado et al. (22)	4	392	12.7	Submerged arc welding
1978	Benoit et al. (23)	15	395	12	Manual arc welding
2013	Schaumann et al. (24)	60	355	4	MAG welding

Results of the statistical evaluation of the “filtered database” along with the corresponding fatigue resistance curves given in prEN 1993-1-9 (1) for the specific constructional detail are presented in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Test results and design fatigue resistance curve for filtered database of transverse butt-weld joints welded from one side

It is evident that reducing the parameter range of the “filtered database” results in less scatter of the results compared to the “full database”. The additional parameters that contribute to the high scatter of the “full database” are analysed in the following.

Based on the results from the “filtered database” depicted in *Figure 1*, the statistical evaluation reveals a characteristic fatigue resistance of 83 MPa at two million cycles. Therefore, for the specimens for which the presence of welding imperfections is unknown, DC 80 that is higher than the value proposed in prEN 1993-1-9 (1) could be suitable. This implies that if an ISO 5817 (6) weld quality B was achieved for all the specimens in the database, the detail category should be higher than 71.

After having analysed results of specimens with unknown quantity of imperfections, the following paragraphs show the assessment of fatigue test results for which weld imperfections were reported in detail. Some of the specimens tested in the “full database” exhibit imperfections, particularly lack of penetration (LOP), present in 88 specimens (21, 24). It is important to note that ISO 5817 (6) quality levels B and C do not permit a lack of penetration. Apart from the presence of LOP (imperfection reported), the specimens studied in *Figure 2* meet all the other conditions of the “filtered database”. *Figure 2* displays the test results and fatigue resistance curves for various percentages of LOP in 12 mm and 20 mm thick plates.

Figure 2: Test results and design fatigue resistance curves for transverse butt-weld joints welded from one side with LOP

A lack of penetration results in a notable reduction in fatigue strength while varying the defect depth “h” from 0 to 31% of the plate thickness. A LOP equal to or less than 10% of the plate thickness has decreased the fatigue strength to 49 MPa at two million cycles, which is remarkable compared to the fatigue strength of the “filtered database” (49 MPa vs. 83 MPa). A LOP ranging between 10% and 20% of the plate thickness leads to a further reduction in fatigue strength to 35 MPa, while a LOP exceeding 20% significantly decreased the fatigue strength to 21 MPa.

Other imperfections were also reported in the “full database” for this type of connection, with less precision regarding their size and distribution. For instance, 78 specimens were identified to have inclusions (25), 16 specimens were found to have a lack of fusion (26), and 16 specimens exhibited porosities (26), with the distribution of pores ranging between 2% and 62% of the weld length, and no information provided regarding their depth. Apart from the reported presence of imperfections, all these specimens, presented in *Figure 3*, verify the other conditions of the “filtered database”.

Figure 3: Test results and design fatigue resistance for transverse butt-weld joints welded from one side with different imperfections

The analysis shows that specimens containing inclusions (81 MPa) and porosities (85 MPa) exhibit a characteristic fatigue resistance almost similar to that of the “filtered database” (83 MPa). However, it is difficult to conclusively determine the impact of inclusions and porosities on fatigue resistance since no information was given regarding their position and size. On the other hand, the lack of fusion in a welded connection reduces the fatigue strength to 62 MPa.

4 TRANSVERSE BUTT-WELD JOINT WELDED FROM TWO SIDES

According to prEN 1993-1-9 (1), three detail categories may potentially be applied for transverse butt-weld joints welded from two sides: DC 112 applies when the welds are ground flush all-around, while DC 90 and DC 80 are acceptable for the as-welded joints with a flank angle higher or equal to 150° and 110° respectively. It is worth noting that measuring the flank angle in practice poses challenges, which raises questions about the feasibility of this requirement and the experimental justifications behind the adopted values. For this type of joint, prEN 1993-1-9 considers a misalignment less or equal to 5% of plate thickness.

For these joints, an analysis was carried out on 2394 tests within the extensive “full database”, with 326 tests meeting the criteria set for the “filtered database”. *Table 3* provides details and references for these selected 326 tests.

Table 3: Filtered database references and information for butt-weld joints welded from two sides

Year	Reference	Number of specimens	f_y [MPa]	Plate thickness [mm]	Welding process
1958	Garcia-Martin et al. (27)	15	265	12.5	Automatic submerged arc welding
1965	Mueller et al. (28)	24	390; 435	20	Submerged arc welding, manual arc welding
1967	Frost et al. (29)	19	433	16	Manual arc welding
1968	Friis et al. (30)	88	250; 375; 400	20; 22.5	Manual arc welding
1969	Reemsnyder (31)	6	320	19	Automatic submerged arc welding
1969	(32)	6	375	14	CO2-metal arc welding
1969	Kunish (33)	28	368	12	Manual arc welding
1970	Odegard et al. (34)	25	298; 392	20	Manual arc welding
1971	Garcia et al. (35)	10	251	15	Manual arc welding
1973	Heckel (36)	3	236	14	Manual arc welding
1975	Kado et al. (22)	6	392	12.7	Manual arc welding
1978	Benoit et al. (23)	26	395	12	Submerged arc welding
1978	Minner et al. (37)	49	499	12	Shielded arc welding
1980	Wylde et al. (38)	9	275	12.5	-
1990	Ohta et al. (39)	7	217	9	Manual arc welding
2009	Polezhayeva et al. (40)	5	390	22	Submerged arc welding

Results of the statistical evaluation of the “filtered database” are depicted in *Figure 4* alongside the fatigue resistance curves for two-sided butt welds given in prEN 1993-1-9 (1). At this point, one should note that the “filtered database” does not cover ground flush welds; hence, a comparison with DC 90 and DC80 is relevant.

Figure 4: Test results and design fatigue resistance curve for filtered database of transverse butt-weld joints welded from two sides

The statistical evaluation of the “filtered database” in *Figure 4* reveals a characteristic fatigue strength of 98 MPa at two million cycles aligning with the requirements of prEN 1993-1-9 (1) for DC 90. While this consistency is promising, it does not confirm whether a quality level B was adhered to in the specimens at that time. To address this, the following sections investigate the effect of different imperfections identified in the specimens within the “full database”.

For butt-weld joints welded from two sides, the “full database” includes specimens with identified imperfections like linear misalignment, inclusions, and lack of penetration. Notably, Wylde and Maddox (38) conducted experimental tests on a 12.5 mm plate thickness with misalignments. *Figure 5* illustrates the impact of misalignment on fatigue resistance. The study analysed 31 specimens, of which 9 were without misalignment and achieved ISO 5817 (6) quality level B. The remaining 22 specimens had misalignment “e” ranging from 3.2 mm to 12.5 mm and exhibited quality levels lower than D of ISO 5817.

Figure 5: Test results and design fatigue resistance curves for transverse butt-weld joints welded from two sides with linear misalignment

It should be noted that the limited number of tests conducted for each misalignment dimension is insufficient to draw accurate conclusions about the fatigue resistance. *Figure 5* displays the test results, indicating a significant effect of linear misalignment. A misalignment of 3.2 mm (25% of plate thickness) reduces the characteristic fatigue strength from 82 MPa to 66 MPa. This decrease in fatigue strength remains consistent as misalignment values increase. One should note that ISO 5817 (6) limits the misalignment to 10% of plate thickness for quality level B.

Within the “full database”, some specimens were identified with other types of imperfections. *Figure 6* shows the test results and fatigue resistance curves for each type of imperfection. This study involves 5 specimens with a 3.2 mm linear misalignment as mentioned in the preceding paragraph (ISO 5817 quality level D), 14 specimens containing inclusions (ISO 5817 quality level undefined) (41), 5 machined specimens with porosity (ISO 5817 quality level lower than D) (42), and 50 specimens with a lack of penetration (ISO 5817 quality level lower than D) (43, 44).

Figure 6: Test results and design fatigue resistance curves for transverse butt-weld joints welded from two sides with different imperfections

According to the imperfections analysed in *Figure 6* the test results reveal a limited reduction in fatigue resistance for the joints with welds containing inclusions. The obtained fatigue strength is 84 MPa, which is lower than the 98 MPa provided by the “filtered database” and between DC 80 and DC 90 given in prEN 1993-1-9 (1) for this type of joint. However, a lack of penetration has a highly detrimental effect on fatigue, reducing the fatigue resistance to 26 MPa. To provide a detailed insight, a LOP ranging from 7% to 15% of the plate thickness decreased the fatigue strength to 82 MPa. A LOP ranging from 15% to 33% have severely reduced the fatigue resistance to 17 MPa.

Finally, the presence of porosity in a machined weld reduces the fatigue strength to 89 MPa, which is well below the fatigue resistance curve recommended by prEN 1993-1-9 (1) (DC 112 for machined weld). Based on the observed results, it is evident that not all imperfections have a similar impact on weld fatigue resistance, which is expected to be characterized by ISO 5817 weld quality level only.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This research examined fatigue tests compiled from multiple sources, each representing a distinct set of experimental conditions, materials and imperfections. The primary objective was to analyse the effect of different imperfections on the fatigue resistance of butt-weld joints. A summary of the findings is presented in *Table 4*. This table shows a first tentative to establish a relationship between weld quality levels provided in ISO 5817 (6) and the fatigue resistance of welded joints. It is of utmost importance to note that the study presented here is limited as not all parameters have been reported in details for all tests. Therefore, the results summarized in *Table 4* should be understood as a starting point helping to identify parameters that are worth to be studied in the future. The quality level “<D” is employed to designate imperfections surpassing the limits defined for ISO 5817 (6) quality level D.

Table 4: Database summary on the link between weld quality levels and fatigue resistance

Imperfection	Number of tests	Quality level (6)	Fatigue resistance at two million cycles	Appropriate DC according to (1)
Transverse butt-weld joints welded from one side				
No reported imperfection	194	Unknown ^a	83	
Lack of penetration	33	D	49	DC 71 if checked by appropriate NDT
	36	< D	29	
Inclusions	78	Unknown	83	DC 36 otherwise
Lack of fusion	16	Unknown	62	
Porosities	16	Unknown	85	
Transverse butt-weld joints welded from two sides				
No imperfection detected	326	Unknown ^a	98	
Lack of penetration	9	D	82	DC 90 if flank angle $\geq 150^\circ$
	41	< D	22	
Inclusions	14	Unknown	84	DC 80 if flank angle $\geq 110^\circ$
Misalignment	5	D	66	
	17	< D	31	
Porosity	5 (machined)	< D	89	DC 112 if machined

^a Quality level could be assumed as B

The weld quality levels defined in ISO 5817 (6) do not always show a significant correlation with the fatigue resistance of welded joints. However, this study identified three key parameters that notably influence the fatigue strength of an imperfect butt-weld:

- **Joint configuration:** the effect of lack of penetration quality level D differs between butt-weld joints made from one side (49 MPa) and those made from two sides (82 MPa).
- **Type of imperfection:** certain types of imperfections, such as a lack of penetration in quality level D, have a less pronounced effect on fatigue strength compared to others, like linear misalignment with the same quality level. For example, in a two-sided butt weld, the fatigue strength is 82 MPa for lack of penetration and 66 MPa for linear misalignment.
- **Quality level:** as expected, increasing the size and quantity of imperfections decreases the fatigue strength of the joint, as illustrated in *Figure 5* for the relationship between linear misalignment and fatigue strength.

Furthermore, other factors, such as residual stress, plate thickness, and welding conditions, can have an influence on the fatigue resistance of welded joints. Therefore, the requirement of a general quality level B for all detail categories in prEN 1993-1-9 (1) does not align with the findings of this study. In the future, additional weld configurations, such as cruciform joints, will be considered. Experiments will also be conducted to expand the scope of this study to include other imperfections and quality level C.

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